

Falcon

Foreseeing the next generation of Aircraft

HYBRID APPROACH USING LATTICE-BOLTZMANN, EXPERIMENTS AND MODELING TO OPTIMIZE FLUID/STRUCTURE INTERACTIONS (FALCON)

WP3 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmark Experiments

D3.1. Evaluation of Existing Industrial Database

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Hans Martin Bleecke
Ramón Abarca Lopez
Fabien Vieuille
Etienne Coetzee

Airbus

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Author(s)	Hans Martin Bleecke (AIRBUS-DE) Ramón Abarca Lopez (AIRBUS-SP) Fabien Vieuille (AIRBUS-FR) Etienne Coetzte (AIRBUS-UK)
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FSI	Fluid-structure interaction
TC	Test Case
LCO	Limit Cycle Oscillation
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

The objective of this report is to provide an experimental database of two of the three experimental test cases that are being considered by the FALCON consortium. These two test cases are experimental tests performed already by Airbus. They are relevant for industrial contexts and are delivered inside the consortium to bridge the gap between academic test cases and industrial relevant ones. It provides a further step in complexity beyond traditional FSI academic test cases available in the literature.

The ultimate goal will be to support the development and validation of FSI solvers with a reliable and highly accurate experimental database.

The two test cases are: A generic high flexible wing test case (TC1) for Limit Cycle Oscillation (LCO) predictions and a generic wing-root seal experiment for aeroacoustics of flow excited structures (TC3).

It serves on the one hand the validation purposes of the newly developed methods in WP2, and on the other hand the hybrid numerical database of WP4.

Figure 1: TC1 Aeroelastic Wing on left and TC3 Wing-root Seal on the right

2. TC1: Aeroelastic Wing

2.1. Definitions

Test case 1 for flutter and LCO identification on a high aspect ratio wing with a tip pod, which was measured in the experimental low speed wind tunnel facility at the University of Bristol and is elaborately described in Ref. [1], a technical report which will be shared with the FALCON partners. Most of this current description here is just a summarising overview and excerpt of [1]. The model was initially set up and measured in 2018. Based on those results, the model was updated with respect to a more aerodynamic design of the tip pod, there were more kulites (for unsteady pressure measurements) installed and the seals between the panels were improved. The structural model was again structurally identified. The geometry and the corresponding structural model shared with FALCON partners represent the latest model status reached in 2024. In the figures 1 and 2 below, the geometry definition of the wing planform and profiling as well as the tip pod geometry is given. In Fig. 3 the shaker assembly and geometry for external excitation of the model is shown. As such a device is not necessary to excite the model in a theoretical simulation, it was decided not to model it.

Fig. 1: Wing planform definition

Fig. 2: Wing tip pod definition

Fig. 3: Shaker assembly and geometry

2.2. Domain Definition

The geometry of the outer contour is defined in Catia along Figs. 1 and 2 and can be used as the basis for surface meshing for ProLB. The wing is set up as a rectangular wing with NACA0015 profiles at the root and NACA 0012 profiles at the tip. The span of the wing is 2.4m and the root chord measures 32cm. Figure 4 shows the geometry in CATIA.

Fig. 4: Geometry of the outer contour surface of the geometry

The geometry contained in the Catia file is ready for mesh generation, no additional cleaning is required. The difference with the original in the wind tunnel is a different axis system used here to accommodate the CFD solvers. The span direction in Catia is the positive y-direction, being it the positive z-direction in the wind tunnel.

A nonlinear intrinsic (SOL400) beam model was used for the structure, Fig. 5, assuming a discontinuous taper along the wing. It was assumed that the wing was fully fixed to the wind tunnel wall. The effect of the tip store was ignored from an aerodynamic viewpoint, but the inertial effects were included for the dynamic computations.

This model is made suitable for coupled simulations doing a mode identification with the new seals that covered the gap between the panels.

Fig. 5: Structural model representing the spar

All the relevant modes were identified in a GVT prior to the wind tunnel test, see Fig. 6 for the in-plane mode identification with the new seals covering the gap between the panels.

Fig. 6: In-plane testing methodology

2.3. Fluid Properties

All experimental and numerical fluid properties are considered to be Standard Atmosphere sea level conditions. The Mach numbers are in the low subsonic range until roughly $M=0.2$ corresponding to a maximum speed of $V=70\text{m/s}$. In the experimental validation cases, the speed never exceeded 50 m/s

2.4. Structure Properties

The structural model represents a nonlinear beam model of the corresponding geometry in Nastran bulk data file format. The structural properties were validated with a GVT test. The model is shared with the partners.

2.5. Experimental set-up

The model was set up in the Filton wind tunnel facility, Fig. 7, where a full range of complimentary sensors were used to measure both structural and aerodynamic data during the tests.

Fig. 7: Model in the Filton wind tunnel facility

The structural behaviour was measured with:

- 3D cameras – 49 targets were attached to the structure at various spanwise and chordwise locations and x,y,z coordinates of each point were measured simultaneously at a sampling rate of 117 Hz.
- Strain gauges – Three sets of strain gauge rosettes were installed at points on the structure that were predicted to experience the largest strains. These were then used for safety monitoring.
- Accelerometers – tri-axial and uni-axis accelerometers were positioned on the leading and trailing edges of several chordwise sections (5, 8, 11 and 12) enabling in-plane, out-of-plane and torsional motions to be measured.
- Wind tunnel balance – full six-component static balance readings were taken throughout the tests giving CL, CD, CM, etc.
- Force gauge – measurement of forces input from the shaker via the stinger at aerodynamic section 3.

For the aerodynamic measurements, the following instrumentation was used:

- Steady pressure tappings – one inboard section (panel 4) was instrumented with 21 chordwise pressure tappings on the upper and lower surface
- Unsteady pressure tappings – one outboard section (panel 10) was instrumented with 17 chordwise Kulites on both surfaces to measure unsteady pressures
- Tunnel measurements – a full set of wind tunnel parameters was continuously monitored during the test including: pressure, temperature, angle of incidence, dynamic pressure, Reynolds number

- Tufts – tufts were placed over the entire upper surface of the wing to enable a visual check on when and where the flow separated.

The shaker assembly was used for exciting the wing configuration with an APS-113 electro-mechanical shaker, positioned below the floor of the wind tunnel, was connected to the wing via a strut which was enclosed with an aerodynamically shaped cover. The shaker was used to excite the structure with either harmonic or “chirp” inputs over a range of frequencies from 0.1 – 17 Hz. A drawing of the shaker layout was shown in Figure 3.

2.6. Experimental results

The conditions of the experimental test points of the 2024 wind tunnel campaign are shown in Fig. 8. In this campaign it was decided to avoid any LCO’s and therefore the velocities and deflections were limited to an, a priori, calculated envelope. The results are all being examined for the preparation of the second wind tunnel campaign that will further investigate the flutter and LCO boundaries at different speeds and angles of attack. The experimental results comprise all the data from the measured instrumentation.

Fig. 8: Test points from 2024 tests. Total number of points shown in brackets.

2.6.1. Fluid measurements

Using experimental results on the following cases in Table 1, theoretical methods can be validated and prove their ability to analyse nonlinear aeroelastic phenomena that will be tested in the upcoming physical experiment.

case	Mach no	alpha [°]	T [K]	V [m/s]	Re	Mass position
38249	0.0823	1.0-5.0 (0.5)	288.15	28	5e5	AFT
38256	0.0882	1.0-5.0 (0.5)	288.15	30	5e5	FWD
38292	0.1142	1.0,2.0,3.0	288.15	39	7e5	FWD
38295	0.1142	1.0,2.0,3.0	288.15	39	7e5	AFT
38302	0.1205-0.1322	1.0	288.15	41,43,44,45	7-8e5	FWD
38305	0.1205-0.1322	3.0	288.15	41,43,44,45	7-8e5	AFT

Table 1: Overview of the 6 numerical validation test points

The test cases 38249 and 38256 are simulated with a variation of the angle of attack from 1 to 5 degrees with half a degree steps. The Reynolds number in the table is based on the reference length of the Mean Aerodynamic Chord (MAC) and varies with the given velocity. In total, this table describes 26 simulations that can be performed. The experimental results are shared with the partners.

2.6.2. Structural measurements

The structural measurements of the GVT can be exchanged for tuning further structural models that will be shared with Airbus in due course of the project.

The structural measurements instrumentation of the wind tunnel test is described in section 2.5. The camera data can be used to calculate the deformed shapes for the respective flow conditions. The accelerometer data can be used to verify the camera data measurements in discrete points. The experimental deformation data can be used as a means to validate the coupled simulations and will be shared with the partners in due course of the project

2.6.3. Global results (i.e: global real measured shapes)

All results are described in an Airbus report Ref.[2], which is an extract from the Airbus internal report, described in [1]

2.7. Acknowledgements

The models and data were obtained from the UK ATI funded project:

<https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=10079510>

2.8. References

[1] Technical Report: High Aspect Ratio Wing - FALCON Data Release, Reference RPT-HARW-2024-2-2, [Etienne Coetzee](#)

[2] Technical Report: High Aspect Ratio Wing - FALCON Data Release, Reference RPT-HARW-2024-2-2-V1.0, [Etienne Coetzee](#)

1. TC3: Wing-root seal

1.1. Definitions

This section is about the TC3 for assessing seal vibration at the fuselage/wing interface. The seal is exposed to a delta pressure leading a detachment and then a vibration of the lip. It is related to a strong aeroelastic coupling of the lip with both airsides environments.

As the seal vibrates, it hits the wing (horizontal plane in the following drawings).

The behavior can be reproduced by isolating the seal, and setting a delta pressure on both parts of the flexible lip.

When the delta pressure raises a threshold, the lip starts elevating. This motion allows the air to migrate to the other side, reducing the delta pressure. Then, the lip goes down to contact the wing again (or ground). Then, the delta pressure raises, starting a new vibration cycle.

The objectives of this use case are:

- To have a numerical tool able to simulate the behavior of the overpressure/underpressure triggering the vibration of the seal.
- To have a numerical tool able to simulate the aeroelasticity behavior, the strong coupling between the seal and the fluid dynamics
- To have a beating frequency similar to flight observation (within the 100-400Hz band)

1.2. Domain Definition

The geometry of the seal is defined in the following drawing

The proposed fluid domain geometries are described in the following drawing. However, limits will be adapted with regards to constraints from the aero-elastic solvers solutions that will be investigated.

Please note that it is a proposed geometry. It has to be adapted following the developed solution.

1.3. Fluid Properties

The fluid properties, as measured in flight tests and simulated by CFD computations, are the following:

- cavity 1 (exterior):
 - P=12 000 Pa
 - Tinf=-55°C
 - Minf=0.84
- cavity 2 and 3
 - pressure to be tuned
 - Tinf=-55°C
 - Minf=0.

The pressures in cavities 2 and 3 must be tuned to trigger the lip to lift up.

Cavity numbers refer to the drawing in the previous part.

1.4. Structure Properties

The seal is modelled using an isotropic material definition (SI units). It is made of elastomer silicone rubber with the following range of properties.

(Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Material_selection#/media/File:Young_vs_density-loglog.svg)

1.5. Experimental set-up

The test case is the reproduction of a flight aircraft. The inlet is the incoming flow above the wing. The seal links the upper part of the wing to the fuselage

The seal must be pre-stressed by $0.2X$ mm in the height direction (see picture)

For the structural dynamics computation, the seal is considered as blocked, no displacement in all directions:

- On the whole top edge
- On both sides

The model can include sensors for measuring the lip displacement function of time in order to detect and derive oscillations amplitude and frequencies.

The property of the air walls for the fluid dynamics computation are the following:

- wing, seal and fuselage walls have a non-slip condition
- other bounds of the domains have a slip condition

1.6. Experimental results

1.6.1. Fluid measurements

Regarding the fluid results, the initial conditions are provided in the previous part. Those fluid properties (pressure, temperature, Mach) have been measured in flight while the seal was beating. They have been confirmed using additional CFD computations (RANS).

1.6.2. Structural measurements

The main behavior to simulate is the aeroelastic coupling between the fluid dynamics and the seal making it oscillating and beating on the wing/ground. This oscillation modelling should allow understanding the key characteristics of a seal design.

Another numerical method has been applied to the same use case. It leads to a beating frequency between 100 and 400Hz pending on seal and flow parameters.

No amplitude of motion or force measurements is available.

2.9. Acknowledgements

The data was obtained from the MAMBO French funded project